
FEDERAL CENTRALISM and NIGERIAN UNIVERSITY GOVERNANCE

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the trend towards intensified centralization and autocracy of decision-making in the Nigerian university system. It scrutinizes the plethora of management organs designed as and employed by managers of the universities. The question is what management concept is applicable to Nigerian universities? Is a uniform concept applicable to all universities? What of the overarching power of the Federal Government which was frequently military in the past and autocratic in its foundation? Is it likely that concepts of freedom in decision-making for universities using decentralization, delegation, deregulation, debureaucratisation, or independence would best suit that Nigerian organization as against an autocratic strong-arm type model? It is imperative to draw a linkage between developments in the federal democratic polity of Nigeria and happenings inside the Nigerian university system and to see the latter as merely a product of the Nigerian ecology. But should the University organization merely mirror its society or blaze-trail into creative intellectual ground-breaking?

KEYWORDS: Federal Centralism, Nigeria, University, Governance

INTRODUCTION

A steady growth of expletives, sometime stinging, at other times incendiary, is frequently used to qualify Nigeria as an entity. Some already consider her as a failed or at least a failing state. To others, it is Africa's 'sleeping economic giant' or a 'deformed giant' Saint William (2004). Nigeria is described as 'one of the most difficult countries in the world for private business' with 'human and cultural conditions' that are antithetic to development. These unsavoury descriptions started primarily with the sustained recurrent military regimes in Nigeria; between January 1966 and October 1979, and January 1983 and May 1999. This protracted military interregnum meant a total abandonment of democratic ethos. Constitutions, Parliaments, the Rule of Law, Basic and Fundamental Rights Features are the regular casualties of each coup d'état announcement. By extension, the freedom of institutions no matter how sacred, is suspended categorically leaving little or no room for negotiated options.

Since the university organization thrives on the foundation of freedom to read, to study, to research, to investigate, to critique, to conclude, it was bound to clash headlong with despotism. The earliest universities were 'free to govern' (Encyclopedia Britannica) themselves though had to finance themselves through fees charged on students. They received Charters from Popes, Emperors, Kings and governments whilst modern universities are financed usually by national, state or private bodies.

For rather compelling circumstances, the British fitted Nigeria into a federal structure consisting of a central government and three regions. There was need for political accommodation amongst the diverse nationalities to enhance a meaningful participation by all in national life. After all in 'many modern states, the emphasis is on bringing government close to the sovereign people through local self-governing institutions' to ensure the promotion of political participation, for effective resource mobilization.³ Adamolekun's argument (2008) was that the regular expectation of devolution in a federal system was completely sidelined in Nigeria with the 'centralisation and uniformity' imposed all through three decades of military rule. There were, subsequent to independence, creation of states and local governments especially by military regimes. Unfortunately, Nigeria's federalism has failed to achieve a credible form of economic prosperity. Indeed the potency and supremacy of the federal government over the component parts – the states and the local governments – have continued to constitute a worrying issue particularly for the progress of higher education in Nigeria.

This paper examines the trend towards intensified centralization and autocracy of decision-making in Nigerian university system. It scrutinizes the plethora of management organs designed as and employed by the managers of the universities. The question is what management concept is applicable to Nigerian universities? Is a uniform concept applicable to all universities? What of the overarching power of the Federal Government which was frequently military in the past and autocratic in its foundation? Is it likely that concepts of freedom in decision-making for universities using decentralization, delegation, deregulation, debureaucratization or independence would best suit the Nigerian university organization as against an autocratic strong-arm type model?

Historical Perspective

Part of the explanations for governance autocracy in Nigerian higher education system as an extension of the autocratic management of the entire country is found in the legacy of highhandedness bequeathed by expatriate colonial law-enforcers pre-independence. During the Enugu Miners' go-slow (on 8th Nov 1948) against peremptory staff dismissals of Nigerian indigenes by the colliery management, ensuing demonstrations and police intervention led to '21 deaths and 51 wounded' Okonkwo (1964) causing reactive demonstrations in Aba, Calabar, Onitsha and Port Harcourt. It was commonplace for government to jail nationalists and journalists agitating for civil and political concessions or for early independence usually for sedition.

Despite the autocratic nature of Nigerian governments pre-independence, the premier university, the University College, Ibadan started on a rational note. Africa's post-independence regimes recognized the importance of higher education early enough, many of such leaders trained in Britain, the United States and elsewhere overseas before returning home. To some therefore, 'No other institutions can contribute as much to the social and economic development of Africa as the university', Cowan (1966). One of the earliest nationalists, Kwame Nkrumah asserted that 'Apart from the State, the university is one of the greatest institutions of man'. In developing countries, higher education is proclaimed as the bedrock, the major catalyst for the take-off, the stability and progress of society, an awareness of the need to copy the developed countries who are deploying an efficacious partnership with the 'knowledge institutions' to trail-blaze into new grounds of science, technology, discovery and problem-solving. So, many developing countries are witnessing the biggest expansion of their higher education in history. This expansion in some countries is being conducted so haphazardly as to procure a 'massification' or 'democratisation' of higher education. For developing countries, the most recurrently used and heard name in this phenomenon is GOVERNMENT.

Government usually acts as the conceiver, the planner, the designer, the builder, the supervisor, the law-giver, the guardian, the provider, the monitor, the all-in-all for the university institution especially for the publicly-owned ones. The history of full sponsorship left Government with a complacency of a father-figure therefore stuck with contentment that all was well. However the basic ethics of the university ideal was being battered and crushed in the process of sustained over-centralised government at the centre which was unwilling and unlikely to concede some of the basic freedoms required by the university organization. Government over-confidence was entrenched especially in the ensuing militarization of the polity. All was well for the universities until the military took over and especially after the civil war 1967-1970. To show the virtual omnipotence of the use of power and military muscle of the ruling governments, the decade 1970-1980 appears as the worst for Nigerian universities in many dimensions to be shown in this paper.

The University of Ibadan Ordinance of 1 Oct 1954 listed the major goals as:

- (a) To manage the pursuit of a regular and liberal course of education,
- (b) To promote research, advance science and learning and to organize, improve and extend education of a university standard,
- (c) To fulfill these objectives, racial and religious qualifications and discrimination were barred except in the preference given to Nigerians during admission.

The composition of Council was expanded to include twenty-four members including the Chancellor. Council was allowed to delegate its powers to other functionaries in the university. A Visitor was appointed with powers to direct a Visitation to ensure that UCI carried out its prescribed functions. A Senate was to replace the former Academic Board. Faculty Boards were also established. Some unease was observable from the presence of nominees of the Visitor, the Governor-General of the country and those of the three Governors-in-Council for each of the three regions. Thus was planted the seemingly ineradicable foundation of government centralist

intrusion for Nigerian universities although the inclusion of regional governors' representatives gave an impression of a federalist equity concept.

The inceptive organizational structure of the University of Nigeria, Nsukka was unique as compared to those of Ibadan, Ife, Lagos, Ahmadu Bello and Lagos Universities and would have remained so but for military take-over in January 1966. For UNN, Dr Nnamdi Azikiwe, its founder and initiator, was intensely personally involved in its pioneering years such that when he was Nigeria's President, he spent close to half of his term of office at the University of Nigeria campus, Fafunwa, (1971). The imprint of American-trained Dr Azikiwe was writ large on UNN so much so that it was structured and patterned after the original American Land Grant Colleges. UNN resolved that its curricula 'should be related to the day-to-day life of the people', it started with six faculties, (Arts, Science, Law, Theology, Engineering and Medicine) to which multiple Institutes were established in:

'Agriculture, Architecture, Diplomacy, Domestic Science, Education, French, Fine Art, Fishery, Forestry, Journalism, Librarianship, Music, Pharmacy, Physical Education, Public Administration, Public Health, Secretarial Studies, Social Work, Surveying and Veterinary Science'

Thus many things were 'unconventional' about UNN, a timely break from the monotony of the Oxbridge model management pattern prevailing in the other Nigerian universities. One other important example was the Course System of instructions – a broadening of the curricula with general studies and skills acquisition which UNN trail-blazed for Nigerian universities. As far as the great Zik was concerned, these unique patterns were being initiated to help correct what he called the 'miseducation of Nigerians by Europeans'.

Origins of Nigerian Centralist Governance Policy

Much of Africa had undergone full-blast colonialism after the gory experience of full-blast slavery across the West African sub-region for centuries, and the consequential abandonment of whatever previous indigenous administrative models that worked well for the pre-colonial empires. What followed for much of the late 19th century and up to the mid-20th century was direct occupation and total government by the British, (this is despite the exoneration of the British who were clearly the most genteel and humane of the major colonial powers who were active occupants of West Africa, that is the Germans, the French, the Dutch, the British). Very little room was permitted for the rudiments of self-rule, except for the use of indirect rule especially in Northern Nigeria. Neither were the colonized encouraged in any form to know the workings of democratic rule. Instead, government-governed relationship was defined by complete monopoly of governing power by British colonial officials, a constantly ruthless suppression of the most minor agitation by workers and by journalists and nationalists seeking some political space towards greater economic, educational and political recognition by the ruling expatriates.

CENTRALISM and FEDERALISM

To reconcile the university organization's pre-occupation with autonomy, many countries adopt the compromise approach of 'decentralised centralism'. This concept tends to strip the power centrepoint from the centre to the periphery, that is, from the central administration to the faculties, departments and committees and to component parts like the staff and student unions. It however distinguishes between decentralization perceived as implementation of decisions taken by the central power, delegation which may imply some conceded local autonomy, devolution involving a grant of authority and responsibility from the centre to the local level. Nigeria has adopted federalism at independence meaning the creation of several decision points in the form of a central government along with several states previously called regions which in presidential system implied several government entities with coordinate and constitutionally distinct jurisdiction. Federalism expects as a concept, basic freedoms especially in a democracy, including multiple parties, freedom of association, of movement, of speech, of participation in civil and political matters, employment. It also implies the flourishing conduct of civil society groups, public and private enterprise performance in an uninhibited atmosphere of a healthy competition for profit or non-profit making.

Government Intervention in Higher Education

There is an apparent consensus the world over that primary and secondary education (along with other pre-tertiary levels) remain uncontested in the domain of national or provincial governments to design and to fund (at least partly). It is also usually accepted that the national government should design, fund, and monitor educational institutions at the tertiary level at least initially. There are reasons for a well-thought-out admixture of independence alongside a reasoned guidance. The concept of independence in English universities was as

strong as to earn the status of 'self-governing corporations' Moodie (1974), in which some 'sovereignty' lies in the university council majority of whom are laymen and therefore represent the public interest. It is nevertheless recognized that an English university (and a Nigerian university) professor is a member of the university senate although this is moderated by the largely layman council.

That solid foundation of university academic freedom has, for developing countries like Nigeria, been challenged by circumstances tending in only one direction; diminished autonomy, reduced social significance leading to a whittled-down relevance reality. Most governments in Nigeria tend to be comprehensively distracted. Their ability to focus flows from situations that tend to fluctuate continuously:

- (a) Absence of a democratic culture which produces an absence of legitimacy,
- (b) Mass discontent deriving from elections that satisfy no one but the declared winners and beneficiaries,
- (c) The bitterness of losers produces protracted lawsuits, recriminations and disaffections for ensuing government,
- (d) The ensuing government engages in some stealthy pacification through a semblance of reaching out to the opposition by infusing a sprinkling (one or two or three members) sometimes lightweight-of opposing political parties into the government by shoving them into low-level advisory (or assistant) positions where they can do little or no harm to the ruling party,
- (e) The ruling clique gets busy thereafter consolidating by engaging in a spasmodic spending spree of the 'dividends of democracy' by using the budget or supplementary budget to award project-contracts. Those contracts go to carefully selected constituencies and deliberately selected contractors for the implementation of disjointedly hatched projects whose execution is laid with the odium of kleptocracy,
- (f) The pervasive ubiquity of the federal government is reflected in various directives from the centre to the states and local governments. These include peremptory summons to the nation's capital for a motley of meetings, to receive directives on matters often within state and local governments' constitutional jurisdiction,
- (g) Each government has to contend with a plethora of issues ranging from the mundane to the serious, the collective to the individual, the solvable to the non-feasible, the long-term to the immediate. Most issues are scalar-chained from the lowest professional administrative officer to the head of division through to the Permanent Secretary, to the Minister, to the Secretary to the Government, to the Chief Executive of the nation.

Institutional and Circumstantial Centralism in University Governance/ Constraints Against Autonomy for Nigerian Universities.

This section attempts a survey of specific national institutions and circumstances that have goaded the country from erstwhile democratic university governance structure into a blatant culture of bureaucratic centralism, governmental autocracy and meddlesomeness in the supervision and management of Nigerian universities.

The concept of autonomy has to be scrutinized intensely. Some questions arise—What is the justification for the thirst, the clamour for autonomy? What intentions and objectives does autonomy meet? Autonomy for universities is defined as their ability to teach including designing what to teach, research and do a continuous public service relatively unhindered and unimpeded. It is essential to identify the organs that constitute the bulwark of hindrances, impediments and frustrations to university autonomy. Each of the agencies identified as impeding of university autonomy are critically unavoidable ie they are necessary agencies for the operations of universities of all kinds, thus they were created to meet perceived needs of government and the citizens although often their performance may lead to criticisms and various challenges for both:

Federal Ministry of Education

Within the Federal Ministry of Education, the Department of Tertiary Education takes direct responsibility for the supervision and management of tertiary education in all its forms. Its broad objectives are to provide tertiary education that is relevant and responsive to the needs of society, in quality and in quantity, providing a well-motivated, highly skilled and qualified staff. Such staff must be productive and knowledgeable, technically competent and adequately prepared for positive contributions to the society.

Its mission is to help the Ministry to achieve the vision of tertiary education in Nigeria through:

- Restricting and re-positioning tertiary education to meet modern challenges,*
- Stabilization of the environment of tertiary education,*

Promoting an environment which facilitates learning and integration of tertiary institutions into the world knowledge network through linkage programmes and improving the competence and efficacy of staff, (www.fme.gov.ng *website for the Federal Ministry of Education, Abuja, Nigeria)*

Principal functions identified as Mission and Vision of the Ministry include;

- Formulation of the national policy on education,
- To muster data for the purpose of planning and financing of education,
- Seeking to maintain uniform standards of education within the country,
- Supervision nationwide through the Inspectorate Services Department to ensure quality education,
- Harmonisation of educational policies and procedures of all States of the country through the National Council of Education,
- Seeking to achieve cooperation on education matters nationally and internationally,
- Developing curricula and syllabuses at the national level in cooperation with other agencies and bodies.

The Federal Ministry of Education persistently moves directly in the eye of the storm, there is hardly any moment that some big controversy or another is not encircling its operations. Many of such crises are endogenous, to the education system (teaching or student matters) but exogenous to the Ministry of Education. The Ministry is constantly confronted with intractable problems incurring it with negative publicity and patent odium from assorted stakeholders, the media, and the public, sometime on issues far beyond its jurisdictional competence.

In any case, the Ministry is often victim of institutional instability as its top functionaries get ferreted away through normal postings of its Ministers, and impromptu and snappy postings of its top bureaucrats. A major feature of Nigeria's governance disability is the peremptory and unplanned tenure instability of top government functionaries. During the ten years 1999 to 2009, the Nigerian newspaper 'the Guardian' observed rather disdainfully that ten ministers in the federal government had served in the Ministry of Education. The article went on to list them and summarize the largely unsavoury or at least untimely circumstances of their exit from that Ministry irrespective of the fact that virtually all of them were highly educated Nigerians, several were academics, some of them delivered creative blueprints for the administration of the Ministry even within their very brief tenures. (Education: 10 Ministers, 10 years of democracy; in the Guardian May 28, 2009, the ten ministers were Prof Tunde Adeniran, Prof Fabian Osuji, Senator Llyel Imoke, Mrs Halima Alao, Mrs Chinwe Obaji, Dr Oby Ezekwesili, Mr Abba Ruma, Dr Igwe Nwachukwn, and Dr Sam Egwu (Oyekanmi 2009, Jun 07)).

The recurrent all-encompassing crises-reeking regime of Nigeria's educational sector has recently been summarized:

'Academic staff union of universities (ASUU) has been locked up in a dispute with the Federal Government over the contentious 2001 agreement which nine Education Ministers have been unable to solve.....Teachers in the 102 Unity Colleges are also on strike, over fears that many of them would become jobless if the schools are sold.....Some Governing Councils appointed just recently to run federal universities have been displaying worrying tendencies. Stakeholders are equally worried about the national primary and junior secondary curricula with a flurry of announcements of governments' intention to do a wholesale restructuring especially the proposed cancellation of the junior secondary portion of the current secondary school system; more students are failing the Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations (SSCE) and the Universities Matriculation Examination (UME), Nigerian Tribune of Sep 19, 2009 claimed through WAEC Head of National Office that 356,981 out of 1.2 million candidates passed with 5 credits including English and Maths in 2009). Doubts are being expressed about the monitoring process for the ambitious Technical and Vocational Education Masterplan, and about the fate of thousands of candidates who fail to make it to the universities after writing the UME owing to the weak carrying capacities of the country's 95 universities (27 federal, 34 state and 34 private).' Oyekanmi (2009).

Yet another nationwide strike by university teachers occurred starting from Dec. 5, 2011. It lasted for 59 days ending on Feb 1, 2012 (Information/Nigerian.org Feb 2, 2012; 'ASUU ends strike, government hails action'). Although broad and specific agreements were reached on the burning issues, the task of a sustainable implementation can be hardly projected into a far-away future. The cost-benefit of strikes remains un-attended and glossed over ie by stakeholders, the academic community and the nation. This

cryptic summary depicts Nigeria's education morass and testifies to the strength of federal centralism. With this much amount of challenges facing every stratum of the education sector, the case is made for an wholistic decentralization and a federalization of federal/state relations to permit authentic, positive and progressive autonomy that gives an adequate pride of place to Nigerian universities and institutions.

West African Examinations Council

The West African Examinations Council was set up in 1952 by the colonial governments of Nigeria, Gold Coast, Sierra Leone and the Gambia. Liberia joined the group in 1974 to produce a 5-country Council. The main goal was:

- To determine examinations required in the public interest in West Africa
- To empower and enable the Council to conduct examinations,
- To confer and award certificates.

There are currently 60 members in the Council representing governments, the universities, secondary schools and other interests. The Council prefers to function through Committees. The major Committees are:

- International Administration & Finance Committee,
- Examinations Committee,
- Appointments Committee,
- Tenders' Committee,
- National Committee (the highest policy-making body of the Council)

The Executive Arm of the Council is headed by the Registrar who coordinates the five national offices. He also supervises the Research Division, the Audit, Finance and Administration Divisions. The Council's funding is mustered through two main sources: examination fees, and subventions from national governments. National subventions are proportioned using various criteria such as the number of candidates and the work-load involved. Consequently, the current ratios ⁴are in WAEC's website (WAECwww.wascnigeria, org/profit),

Nigeria	54.25%
Ghana	30.01%
Sierra Leone	06.91%
The Gambia	06.54%
Liberia	02.29%

WAEC is an international examinations body for five major countries in West Africa. It discharges the role of conducting national examinations especially the West African School Certificate. Over the years, strident complaints about various problems of examination leakages, mishandling of examination arrangements, flooded the countries including Nigeria. These were compounded by an explosion of numbers of candidates. The ensuing anxiety led to the establishment by Nigeria of its own National Examinations Council (NECO) in 1998. NECO was a product of recommendations of the Sogbetun Commission (1977), the M. S. Angulu Panel (1982), the Osiyale Committee (1993) and the Etsu Nupe Panel, all intending to relief WAEC of some of its burdens.

WAEC was originally intended to serve the five member-countries and has apparently sustainably discharged that service despite criticisms and challenges. The concept of federal-centralism has been re-affirmed in its local national operations in Nigeria, to the extent that its operations nationally fit into the unitary centralist posture of governance structure. The member countries need a cross border agency like WAEC for greater credibility and assumed reputation. The former regions and the current states of Nigeria have apparently accepted WAEC operations with hardly any serious agitations for its disbandment or its replication by Nigeria's multiple states despite occasional criticisms about its perceived shortcomings.

National Board for Technical Education

The National Board for Technical Education was set up to handle all aspects of Technical and Vocational Education outside university education. It was created through Act no. 9 of January 1977 to provide minimum

standards and curricula for technical and vocational training. The Board comprises representatives of employers, workers, polytechnics, colleges of technology, vocational training and technical teacher institutions, federal ministries, states, the Industrial Training Fund and the National Science & Technology Development Agency. It seeks to promote good quality technical education through the production of skilled technical and professional manpower, to reduce unemployment and poverty, adequate linkages with industry and sustain the national economy. It is also to provide encouragement for women to enter fields of technical education. The Board regulates the programs offered by the technical institutions at secondary and post-secondary levels leading to a variety of qualifications including some linked to overseas institutions. It sometimes goes into networking arrangements with external bodies like the UNESCO to strengthen technical and vocational education (TVE).

National Teachers' Institute

The National Teachers' Institute was established in the 'golden' centralizing decade ('70-79), in 1974 to upgrade and improve the quality of Nigerian education particularly targeting the Universal Primary Education Scheme which was then on the drawing board. The Institute established study-centres in all states to achieve the central objective of improving teacher education nation-wide. The Institute thus directly encouraged non-graduate teachers to improve and attain graduate and postgraduate qualifications.

Joint Consultative Committee on Education

This is an independent body of professional educators and specialists meeting to offer composite advice to various agencies including Federal and State Ministries of Education, Universities, Institutes of Education, WAEC and other education agencies. Its main functions are 'influencing educational development in the country, offering professional views in order to evolve 'a harmonious national educational system' (ministry of education website; www.onlinenigeria.com/links/LinksRead Print. asp).

Education Tax Fund

The Fund was established through Decree no 7 of 1993 which enforces a payment of 2% of profits of limited liability companies registered in Nigeria as education tax. The application of the proceeds was proportioned as follows:

Higher Education 50%, Primary Education 40%, Secondary Education 10%

The Fund has since been re-designated as Tertiary Education Trust Fund. The Federal Inland Revenue Service assesses and collects the Education Tax whilst the Fund 'disburses the amounts to educational institutions at Federal, State and Local Government levels'. It also monitors projects executed by the 'institutional beneficiaries' (<http://tetfund.gov.ng/index.php>).

As a reaffirmation of the concept of federal centralism, the establishment and operations of the ETF are under the authority of a Board which is itself a parastatal under the Federal Ministry of Education. Some of the state governments and institutions often wonder why the state indices are not an effective factor in the distribution formula. Also there is often criticism on the spread of the distribution of the proceeds. A similar controversy has dogged the sourcing and application of the Value-Added-Tax (VAT) by the Federal Government as well as the criteria for the choice and spread of institutions selected for assistance. Nonetheless, the ETF is regarded as making a major contribution to the funding of various projects and programme funding of the higher institutions.

Students' Loan Board

The Nigerian Student Loan Board was initially established in 1972. The purpose was to help finance undergraduate and graduate studies locally and overseas. It gave out over N46million by 1992, but suffered from a cripplingly low rate of recovery until the scheme was suspended. It was then replaced by the Education Bank.

The Education Bank was to serve as intermediary in the education credit market. It was to identify, and enhance private sector resources for education funding. It was also to give out student loans, and loans for publishing, for equipment leasing, project financing, fund mobilization and advisory educational services, Dawodu (2007). The Federal Government tended to pursue a hard belief that it could single-handedly bear the burden of funding. When loans were administered, that assisted in providing increased student enrolment and access to higher education. Even the World Bank expressed support for the loan scheme. It did not last for long, it was replaced

with the Education Bank through Decree no 50 of 1993 which was intended to harness private sector resources , intermediate in the country's education credit market, reduce total reliance on the Government. It has not been popularly successful largely because of the recovery capacity.

National Council on Education

Like all major Ministries and Departments within the federal bureaucracy, the national planner for education is the National Council on Education. The Council comprises all Ministers/Commissioners of Education and the Joint Consultative Committee on Education. It is the highest decision-making body in the education sector.

Joint Consultative Committee on Education

An independent body of professional specialists. It advises the Federal and State Ministries of Education including Units, Colleges of Education, Institutes of Education, WAEC and other education agencies. It was established in 1955.

NURTURING A CULTURE OF DEPENDENCY

The oil boom of the 1970s, militarization of the polity, occasional internal discord within the university system, the proliferation of universities arising from the proliferation of state governments which wanted their own institutions and the mass production of largely eligible candidates seeking university admission all led laid the groundwork for increasing dependency on the part of the universities, on the federal government. This dependent status makes universities endemically vulnerable to the whims and vagaries of Government functionaries. Government of course seemed to relish the implied though subtle subservient role of the universities whilst the universities appear to tolerate the new role complacently even if uncomfortably. Some instances are prominent:

At the end of 1977, the Federal Government basking in the new oil revenue euphoria, abolished tuition fees in the universities completely and unilaterally. Even accommodation fees were pegged at N90 per session whilst meals were to cost no more than 50 kobo per student per meal. The decision was apparently not preceded by calculations of potential cost and consequences, nor were relevant stakeholder views openly sought. That single announcement has procured uncertainty, instability and complications in university governance in Nigeria since then. The implications of a tuition-free higher education based on decisions reached at the apogee of the oil boom, has remained a virtually irreversible fixation with an overwhelming impact on the sector. This is especially true as the income and revenue generation capacity of the university was virtually crippled amidst ominous economic circumstances. Two factors tended to have exacerbated the miscalculations of the tuition-free decision of the federal government:

- The country entered into its first major economic downturn in the late 1970s a few years after the then Head of State had flaunted Nigeria's newly-found oil wealth in the face of the world by an over-confident declaration that Nigeria's problem was not finding money by on how to spend it, Ade-Ajayi (2002).
- The military government driven by the over-confidence of a nouveau riche status not only took over four regional universities summarily, but established seven additional ones 'without the benefit of prior planning committees to define the identity and feasibility of each institution'

The powerful status of the Federal Minister of Education who supervises the NUC and the Ministry is recognized as playing a major role in decision-making within the education sector. Along with the NUC both agencies would appear to be the anchor for federal centralism.

A REINVIGORATED NATIONAL UNIVERSITIES COMMISSION

The need for a coordinating agency for Nigerian universities became imperative with the establishment of additional universities following Nigeria's political independence in 1960 and the findings of the Ashby Report in 1960-'Investment in Education; the Report of the Commission on Post-School Certificate and Higher Education in Nigeria'. The NUC was established in 1962 as an advisory agency in the Prime Minister's (or Cabinet Office), to show the importance of higher education. With a profound clairvoyance, the Western Region's Commissioner for Education, Dr S D Onabamiro pleaded strongly for a federated NUC that:

'the proposed Commission should in its composition follow the present pattern of regional representation in the Councils of the existing federal institutions of higher education; two members should be appointed by the Governor-in-Council of each of the three Regions. It is only in this way that

the interests of the Regions can be safeguarded by ensuring that the Regions are represented on the Commission by persons in whom they have confidence' Fafunwa (1971).

The intention was to have an NUC that would provide a 'buffer mechanism' protecting the interests of the government and those of academia, a buffer status implying that government interventions would be limited and take into account university credo of consensualism, collective decision-making and inclusiveness. It is noticeable that developing countries appear to maintain a robust involvement of government in university governance.

These events were themselves followed by the emergence in 1974/5 of a re-empowered National Universities Commission. In 1974, amidst the euphoria of an incipient oil boom and a 1967-1970 civil war victory by the federal government under the military, Decree no 1 of 1974 was promulgated empowering the NUC to set requirements for accreditation of universities. The new NUC was headed by Chief Simeon Adebayo leading a 19-man Commission with Dr Jubril Aminu as Executive Secretary. The nature and dynamics of the performance of the NUC seemed to have strengthened the position that the 1970s and 1980s provided the biggest test for Nigerian university autonomy and the entrenchment of federal centralism at the expense of university autonomy. This development was certainly assisted by the proliferation of university institutions and by massification of student numbers by government and agencies in response to local and political demands for university places. Today's NUC is a parastatal under the Federal Ministry of Education itself under the Federal Executive Council. Its main functions are:

- (a) Granting approval for all academic programmes run in Nigerian universities,
- (b) Granting approval for the establishment of all higher educational institutions offering degree programmes in Nigerian universities,
- (c) Ensure quality assurance of all academic programmes offered in Nigerian universities,

Its main departments are Academic Standards; Inspection & Monitoring; Research & Innovation; Student Support Services; Executive Secretary and Management Support Services, NUC website; (www.nuc.edu.ng/pages.asp?id,27).

More importantly, it harmonised and centralized the modus operandi of all Nigerian universities. This centralisation was an affront to some who considered it a piece of 'heresy' and a 'dangerous philosophy'. Nevertheless, the system survived then and now.

There have been supplementary Decrees and laws giving further powers and responsibilities to the NUC or decisions taken to expand the scope of functions of the NUC just as the expansion of university education through the establishment of more universities by the government and private groups and individuals procured more duties and challenges for the NUC. Decree no 9 (National Minimum Standards and Establishment of Institutions {Amendment} empowered groups and individuals to set up universities. This was to reverse the 1984 Decree which had summarily abolished and prohibited existing and proposed private universities. Several laws were promulgated at various times to meet various needs all amounting to strengthening the NUC and the federal government and sustaining the concept of federal centralism.

AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITIES COORDINATION AGENCY

To show the capacity of muddling inside federal centralism, the Federal Military Government established through Universities of Agriculture Decree no 48 of 1972 the Agricultural Universities Coordinating Agency (AUCA) similar to but parallel to the NU, Njoku (2002). It was to supervise under the Federal Ministry of Agriculture three relatively young Federal Universities of Agriculture at Abeokuta, Makurdi and Umudike. (The Federal Government put their supervision not under the NUC or the Ministry of Education). This situation was reversed through Decree no 11 of 1993 which harmonized provisions for all laws in federal universities. It must have become obvious that that new body would have procured some confusion and inconsistency.

The consequences of this straight-jacketed subversion of democratic decision-making tenets have been largely harmful to the institutions. This precipitous pathway paved by the Federal Government procured ominous repercussions. Some of these were crisply summarized by a former Vice Chancellor thus:

- (i) a social and moral decline with university communities,
- (ii) the non-availability of development, maintenance and running costs, in particular academic and research facilities became inadequate or of poor standard,

- (iii) the collapse of the Naira with consequent deterioration in the standard of living of staff and students,
- (iv) the dwindling superstructure of expatriate staff and students resulting from the above, and leading to the loss of the universities' international flavor,
- (v) industrial unrest usually at the national level, as well as student unrest, (Makanjuola 2003).

The invisible but pervasive effect of an almost beggarly subservience of the universities coincided with additional contemporary subordination of the institutions to governmental bureaucracy. That seeming helplessness started during the military regime which also assumed powers to itself and the subjugation of legal organs especially the University Senate.

JOINT ADMISSIONS AND MATRICULATION BOARD (JAMB)

The end of the Nigerian civil war (1970), the emergence of the country's oil-based financial buoyancy and the 1967 creation of twelve states out of the erstwhile four regions, led to a thirst for more university institutions in the new states. Apart from the existing six universities including the four regional universities taken over ie UNN, UNIFE, ABUZ and UNIBEN; the Federal Government simultaneously set up seven new universities to spread 'the goodies' to each state ie Jos, Calabar, Sokoto, Kano, Ilorin, Maiduguri and Port Harcourt. Till then, each university conducted its own admission process either using direct entry (for candidates with the GCE Advanced Level or the HSC passes) or concessional examination-based entry (for those with relevant pass grades in relevant School Certificate or GCE Ordinary Level subjects. The system was eventually criticised as wasteful, disorderly and uncoordinated (Jamb website, <http://www.jambng.com/history.php>). This formed a compelling background for setting up not just the JAMB but also the reinvigorated NUC. For the former, the Federal Government set up a committee to examine the whole issue of university entrance examination processes under the chairmanship of Chief M S Angulu. This kind of decisive intervention was easy for a military, centralizing government even if decisions are taken summarily without recourse to background dialogue and committee discourses pertinent to university governance.

Set up through a 1977 Decree, it is responsible for the conduct and general management of the conduct of matriculation examinations for admission into all Nigerian universities, polytechnics and colleges of education. A subsequent Amended Decree no 2 of 1988 and the Amended no 33 of 1989 extended the jurisdictional ambit of JAMB which was empowered:

- to conduct Matriculation Examinations for entry into public and private tertiary institutions,
- to appoint examiners, moderators and invigilators,
- to place qualified candidates into tertiary institutions based on vacancies available in each, guidelines of each institution, preferences of candidates for courses and for institutions,
- collate and disseminate information.

Part of the intentions of JAMB as an idea was to centralize admissions, by whittling down the exclusive powers of each University Senate. It was also a means of infusing the quota system into admissions to recognize the needs of 'educationally disadvantaged states' which could not easily meet their manpower requirements using the conventional criteria. Thus the existing quota system was altered to allow JAMB reserve 20% admission for 'educationally disadvantaged states', 30% for students in 'immediate geographical or catchment area', 10% for the Vice Chancellor's discretion and the balance of 40% for merit, Ekundayo (2005). The ensuing controversy following these novel arrangements drew more opprobrium for JAMB than for Government the initiators but nevertheless confirmed government's centralizing tendencies.

There is increasing unease about the efficacy, correctness, efficiency and adequacy of JAMB operations being voiced in several quarters especially complaints from stakeholders. This resentment rose in so much crescendo that key actors in the education industry demanded a profound solution to the crises of public confidence in JAMB with some asking for its abolition entirely. Some of the causative factors can be summarized as:

Allegations that JAMB examinations were prone to fraudulent handlings by examiners who colluded with candidates and parents to cheat,

Allegations that candidates were awarded results sometime without seating for the examination or using impersonation to sit for examinations,

Allegations that wrong and unqualified candidates were sometime issued with letters of admission to universities improperly and fraudulently.

JAMB's decisive status in the admission process of Nigeria's tertiary education has therefore come under frequent criticisms:

- it is another demonstration of Nigeria's federal centralism,
- it helps to foster the muddling and the corruption in the admissions process and therefore in the dwindling quality of Nigeria's tertiary education,
- it helps to directly weaken the autonomy of the universities and other tertiary institutions,
- it helps to absorb barely mature matriculants who would have probably needed to pass through the Higher School Certificate or GCE Advanced Level maturation process.

In sum, JAMB demonstrates the diminution of the powers of the University Senate to admit students into courses just as NUC presents a major diminution of the powers of the University's Senate to approve courses and programmes designed for teaching and research in tertiary institutions. In recent times further criticisms have surged up against JAMB:

- JAMB's fierce opposition to the continued use by tertiary institutions of pre-degree programmes to reduce JAMB's admission powers. JAMB would prefer that all candidates for entry into tertiary institutions should pass through only JAMB's examinations.
- JAMB in 2009 announced its intention to scrap JAMB's annual examinations separately conducted for universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education. Instead, JAMB eventually replaced it in 2010 with a 'Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination UTME'. JAMB's intention was to remove existing dichotomy between polytechnics and university graduates, reduce costs of sitting several examinations, restore the dignity of teachers and holders of Higher National Diploma in the country. By JAMB's plan, candidates would pick six institutions two from each category, so candidates would, if unable to secure university admission, be considered for admission into other levels ie the Polytechnics or Colleges of Education, Nigerian Tribune (2009/4/20),
- JAMB's decision to change some candidates' scores after having released their results. This result-tampering happened with the 2009 results and caused some worry on the part of stakeholders who felt it would be better to delay result-release for some one or two extra weeks to avoid embarrassing corrective action like this, Nigerian Tribune 2009/5/07. This new Examination has been held for two years. There is evidence of a speedy release of results, time would tell whether the trend of candidates' preferences and the culture of malpractices have been positively affected by the new move

JAMB and the Problem of Access to Higher Education

There is widespread suspicion that JAMB is patently unable to meet popular demand for university places, the issues involved relate also to Governments' policies on higher education. There is nevertheless some consensus that JAMB has performed creditably well in its first two decades despite the multiplication of university institutions, the proliferation of graduates of secondary school leaving aspirants seeking university admission, the realization by parents (and students) of the critical importance of higher education. This caveat has often led to desperation by many and criminal acts by a few. It also led to the campaign for the introduction of post-UME screening tests by all Nigerian universities. Its initial major advocate reportedly presented a case thus:

"But Chief Afe Babalola (SAN) the former Chairman of Governing Council for the University of Lagos, could not continue with the flaws in JAMB. He convinced his colleagues on the need for a post-UME, an idea that generated a lot of discrepancies between university authorities and the JAMB. The Board under Professor Dibu Ojerinde had argued that it had the solitary right to conduct examination for any candidate seeking admission to any of the Nigerian university. It also argued that the JAMB Board the only body which could issue letter of university admission had to watch in 2004 as its hitherto awesome powers were shared with universities and tertiary institutions as they annually conduct fresh additional examinations described as screening for intending entrants irrespective of candidates' performance at JAMB's own examination." The universities' craving for a better voice in the admission process is being largely met although other criticisms have surged up to assail the post-JAMB screening tests. The candidates and critics of the tests insist that the institutions are guilty of excessive charges (the federal government recently intervened by pegging the limit of charges to N1,000 per student), others feel it is entirely exploitative to subject candidates to a multiplicity of examinations just to seek admission to tertiary institutions.

STATE-OWNED UNIVERSITIES

In terms of the propensity for persistent interference in governance, state owned universities are probably worse than federal universities. There are cases of state governors and governments dabbling in the selection of vice chancellors, deans, heads of departments, director of programmes, including principal officers at will. Some Chancellors and Pro-Chancellors 'stay permanently in their offices on campus seeing to day-to-day administration' and encouraging some union officials to see them on issues relating to internal governance of the university rather than see the VC or designated officials, Dawodu (2007).

PRIVATELY-OWNED UNIVERSITIES

There were private universities before and by 1979 . The Buhari regime abolished all 26 of them for various reasons. The Babangida regime reopened and relegalised them, leading to a flood of 40 applications out of which the only 3 (Igbinedion, Babcock and Madonna) were licensed. Subsequent intense pressure led to the floodgate of applications especially after 1999, there are currently about 60 of them. The most prominent reasons were; a growing social demand for increased access by qualified candidates, incessant strikes in public universities by staff, public universities insistence on a final retirement benchmark of 65 years for academic staff, need for highly-skilled labour force especially in professional areas of ICT, Accounting, Banking and Finance, Insurance, and the Social Sciences; the need for private/public collaboration in education funding, the need to meet demand especially for access for products of the UBE scheme. Decision-making in private universities are private-sector-compliant so there is a tendency for rational decision-making, cost effectiveness, less waste, strike aversion and a higher probability of meeting market demands. Unavoidably there are cooperative trends in both private and public universities, especially in the area of staffing, the private universities depend on the older public universities for experienced academic staff who teach part-time often in the private ones.

KEY ISSUES

There is increasing cynicism about the future of the Nigerian nation and its higher education system. Yet very little panaceas appear to be available in the immediate future even as very drastic remedies are required especially the need to curb increasing federal centralism.

The ongoing intensified federal centralism has produced largely impotent state governments swirling around an over-strong, militarized, Olurode (2009),and buoyant federal government. The consequences for this lop-sided structure on higher education cannot be adequately quantified. A prominent Unilag Sociology Professor recently asserted and ascribed Nigeria's governance deficiency to the Federal Government's failure 'to meaningfully invest in human capital and adequately respond to their yearnings'. He surmised that the most active states in the recent Boko Haram crisis in Northern Nigeria ie Bauchi, Borno, Kano and Yobe were the states that had the lowest number of students enrolled in Nigerian universities.The educational, social and economic costs of excessive centralism of governance structure can hardly be successfully measured.

The gleaming and glorious era of Nigeria's first republic (1960-1966) seems difficult to recreate. This era consisted of a vigorous, robust and purposefully healthy competition for development amongst the three regions (later four) have remained possibly the most productive era of Nigeria's statehood in terms of economic development and without oil as a major income resource. For Nigerian higher education, T A Ekundayo amidst several analysts concludes that 'in the 70's, Nigeria can boast of an internationally well-regarded higher education system, offering instruction of an international standard in a number of disciplinary areas.....It also served as a magnet for students from neighbouring countries', Ekundayo (2007).

The leadership capacity shown by the leaders of the three original main political parties (of the eastern, the western and the northern regions)- in the 1960s exhibited the most fervent, austere and selfless example-setting for the people of their regions, even amidst limited national unity and guidance by erstwhile colonial masters.The possibility of effectively tapping the enormous human and material capital resources in any meaningful extent was frittered away and remains a mirage till date as the states are effectively stifled and constrained by the central government.The universities are smarting under the yoke of a powerful NUC, itself gasping under a powerful Federal Ministry of Education, itself grappling with a constant flow of hard core political pressure.

One major deficiency of Nigeria's governance is a grotesquely skewed nature of its fiscal federalism. This has caused acute dissent and discord since the end of the Nigeria's civil war. The derivation principle in 1966 at the

end of Nigeria's first military coup was structured thus (information furnished by Chief Omowale Kuye, fmr federal permanent secretary):

(a) Derivation based on resource produced per region	50%
(b) Allocation to the Federal Government	20%
(c) Allocation to Pool for regions based on population, School children enrolment, etc	30%

This fairly effective formula worked well but was 'suspended' by the military which needed all the nation's resources to fight the 1967 Civil War. There has never been a credible redress or return to the pre-civil war resource allocation formula. This is despite hues and cries and relentless crises especially in the Niger Delta which produces over 80% of the oil revenues that feed the Nigerian economy.

Current derivation ratio remains 13% even though the oil producing states and communities have vociferously demanded a much higher ratio abortively. The revenue allocation formula profoundly strengthens the current concept of Nigeria's federal centralism. Along with this fiscal superiority has been a widespread and largely whimsical allocation and re-allocation of functions by successive military regimes to reinforce the Federal Government and to weaken the states and local governments' jurisdictional portfolio. Thus even though there are repeated claims of Nigeria being a federal country, the truth is the country has leaned far more towards a de jure federal but a de facto unitary system.

THE WEAKEST PHASE OF NIGERIAN UNIVERSITY GOVERNANCE

The 1970s proved the apogee of the assault and battery, the relegation and subordination of Nigerian university system. The 'warfare' touched all component members, staff, students, academics, administrators, even Senate and Council members. This is not necessarily unique to Nigeria, it is a virtual Africa-wide phenomenon; 'with the government in many countries having assumed the power to appoint and dismiss the Vice Chancellor, governance in the universities has thus become a purely state control system...' For instance University Councils were unilaterally stripped of powers to appoint and remove Vice Chancellors. That power was conferred on 'the Head of the Federal Military Government' Onyenoru (2004) as against formerly the Joint Committee of Senate and Council. The Visitor became a decisively active part of the decision-making and top management organogram whilst the Vice Chancellor became involuntarily responsible to the Head of the Federal Military Government and by extension the Minister and Ministry of Education and the National Universities Commission.

The NUC was re-named –through Decree no 1 of 1974 which produced a 'highly centralized university system' with powers '...to dictate what to teach and the number of students to be admitted into Nigerian universities' Benjamin (2001). That Decree and subsequent 1988 amendment seemed to have completed the rout of university autonomy in Nigeria. This centralization was an affront to some who considered it a piece of 'heresy' and 'a dangerous philosophy' Ade-Ajayi (2008). Nonetheless, the system has survived then and now even if sometimes wobbling and gasping.

There were directives or 'advice' urging the universities to absorb greater (sometime specific) numbers of students in annual admission exercises to try and address the unstoppable pressure from students with five or more relevant School Certificate credits who were prima facie qualified having gone through JAMB examination or potential beneficiaries of the quota system. The frequent government intervention through directives to universities to admit on the basis of a 60 to 40% ratio in favour of Sciences (over the Arts and Social Sciences) was hardly achievable since the inflow from secondary schools was usually inadequate and lopsided in favour of the Arts and Social Sciences. This was again consequent to the associated problems of shortage of teachers, laboratory deficiencies as well as infrastructure, inspection and other deficiencies inherent in available primary and secondary school products that fed into tertiary education.

The recurrent recourse by university teachers to the use of industrial action as an attack response to Government's perceived insensitivity to the needs of academia has seldom produced a comprehensive and sustained happy ending. Following the acute national economic distress after the Nigerian civil war (inflation, dislocation of peoples and widespread suffering and agony on the part of direct and indirect victims), Government resolved to employ hard-line solutions. It bye-passed the university councils and ordered striking teachers to resume work or face dismissal or ejection from the university's residences within 72 hours. Many complied, some self-evicted themselves from official campus residences leaving with badly battered feelings of

defeat. To restore such dignity, many planned to execute resolves to build or buy their own personal properties at the soonest to avert repeated humiliation.

The Federal Government assumes, presumes and proclaims its ownership of federal universities. As consequence it creates, maintains, and frequently reinforces the agencies established to 'keep the universities in line'. Some writers assert the age-worn cliché about the piper being able to choose to 'dictate the tune', some insist that government should be able to pay to academics 'what it deems fit'. Others insist that 'the federal government does not own the universities, they belong to the people of Nigeria' Ojo-Ade (2009/9/8), who are expected to be served by politicians elected into office to construct, develop and maintain institutions towards national growth. Indeed distinguished American higher education expert Clark Kerr emphasized that for universities to join 'the really international world of learning', they would need to do so with merit, not on politics, but on 'a good deal of autonomy' to enhance dynamism, Saint William (2003). It is difficult to separate Nigerian office holders from 'their office' as each passionately and persistently talks of 'my office', 'my Permanent Secretary' as if they are indeed properties acquired, inherited or purchased with a conclusive ownership title.

It is important to observe that once specific powers and privileges are conferred on Nigerian institutions or functionaries, the probability of accepting their relinquishment is profoundly remote. This is irrespective of whether the circumstances and justification for the privileges and power have become obsolete. The chronic conservatism and complacency in the use of power is pervasive in Nigerian public office. This is why it appears impossible to surrender to a victorious candidate in an election, pay up debts owed to banks, concede justice to the needy and the poor, evacuate a cosy office for a successor.

Various scholars have documented several acts by government applying direct intimidation and intervention in affairs and issues that were essentially domestic to the universities. Some involve an arbitrary use of power by military regimes in the form of summary termination of the appointment of professors in Ibadan in 1978 and 1990, in Lagos in 1980. In all cases the terminations were executed without due process, Onyeonuoru (2004). However, Government interventionist proclivities are often enhanced or procured by mismanagement on the part of individual university authorities. Such indiscretions and misgovernance are recurrent happenings in many of the universities as has been well documented by Egbokhare and Ujomu both of Unibadan, Ujomu (2001).

There were other multiple instances where Government took decisions that directly eroded the powers of the Senate of the university leaving the university organs virtually impotent and prostrate before government functionaries. One major instance was the establishment in a 1977 Decree, of the Joint Admission and Matriculation Board. It was empowered to determine and prescribe for student-intake. The latest instance is the unilateral renaming of the University of Lagos as Moshood Kashimawo Abiola University to honour a truly heroic man considered a martyr for Nigerian democracy arising from the Babangida military subversion of his election victory result in June 1993. This event is still generating fervent opprobrium and dissent. Universities' Senate becomes virtually a by-stander in major academic decisions, the core of university autonomy.

CONCLUSION

Nigeria has not been known for bearing a systematic planning ability. Thus, except for the UCI whose foundation was based on a careful planned study by the colonial government (the Asquith, Ashby and Elliot Commissions), higher education evolved rather accidentally or purely as a heuristic reaction to 'fortuitous' events. Such events included the oil boom, military rule, creation of states and attendant agitations by state governments and vocal communities for new universities. Thus some universities were created like an amenity and announced without background study or feasibility of its long and short-term implications. Internally, the University organization adopts practices of consultation, consensus, decentralization, and conflict-resolution especially with the intensive use of the committee system and the representativeness of the bodies of the community onto formal organs of management. However it is not a perfect organisation, nor is it proving consistently capable of solving its domestic and national problems. The missing link is inadequate Autonomy amidst other challenges.

Several conscious Nigerians appreciate the negative effects of excessive federal power gulping up much of the political space and preventing a real move for an authentic federal structure to facilitate genuine plurality and

productive diversity. Whilst discussing the stubborn refusal of the federal government to adjust the revenue derivation formula to favour the Niger-Delta region, Major-General Ishola Williams (2009) recently lamented:

“What obtains in Nigeria is that the central government bears all the problems while the states are doing nothing, forgetting that development ought to begin from the grassroots. If development should start from the grassroots, then people should then use the resources at their disposal to develop themselves.”

The classical definitions of federalism presume the collection of a cluster of ‘autonomous building blocks’ where ‘there is no boss or big brother’, the management of equal federating units as equal partners. A ‘Vanguard’ analyst recently begged ‘for a federation’ writing that ‘in a normal federal system,...the building blocks are autonomous’....; ‘each federating unit or state should have the powers to run its internal administrative machinery the way it thinks best’ Lakemfa (2009). The Nigerian Independence Constitution of 1960 contained the characteristic features of a federal system of government; each of the component parts – the federal and the regional governments each had a bicameral legislature, whilst the Exclusive Legislative List comprised functions reserved for the federal government, the regions had their own residual list and separate constitutions. In each case the executive authority was the Queen but those powers were delegated to the head of each government ie the Prime Minister at the federal level and the Premier at the regional level, Oyediran (2009). However the reality on the ground is an unwillingness of successive federal governments to relinquish a jot of federal power especially since the intervention of the military since Jan 1966. Dougl Anele (2009) lamented that the Nigerian federal government has over the years ‘emasculated the constituent geopolitical configurations that make up Nigeria, and made itself a big Santa Claus to the states’. State control of higher education has tended to undermine the principles of good governance, buffer mechanisms including the agencies have not worked much, thus ‘the involvement of politicians has generally politicized higher education, widened the possibility for corruption and mismanagement www.net/report/Chapter3.htm; Higher education in developing countries.

Reviewing the totality of multiple and insidious government interferences in university governance in the 1970s, Peter O Adeniyi, a former Vice Chancellor, concluded that:

“the centralized policies were mechanically and uniformly implemented across all institutional levels, notwithstanding the different needs and requirements of each university. Thus the intellectual search for matching, mixing and switching of strategies to improve the performance of each university was largely foreclosed” Adeniyi (2008).

University autonomy cannot evolve where Universities are prevented from doing many things on their own initiative, of their own free will, including the choice of raising revenue to meet part (if not all) of their financial needs. This perennial decision to forbid Nigerian public universities from charging tuition fees and charging beyond ninety naira per annum for boarding fees, imposes on them a status of perpetual dependence on government or on donors for all needs. It is obvious that ‘No people can be genuinely free, so long as they look to others for their deliverance. The ability to help oneself may be the first action that leads to freedom’ Ashimolowo (2008). It is the position of this paper that authentic freedom for universities to breathe, to teach, to research, to take academic and allied decisions, to contribute to a knowledge economy and improve society, is essential and obligatory for a Nigeria that needs to grow into modernity and progress and tear itself from ‘a death row’, Iwuanyanwu (2012).

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